

Wheat Ear Detection in RGB and Thermal Images Using Deep Neural Networks

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Abstract. The number of farmers who use smart phones is increasing rapidly and furthermore RGB and thermal cameras are becoming more and more available either as smart phone gadgets or as integrated parts of the smart phone. Using them, farmers could have early information about the wheat yield. Currently, counting ears on part of a field and extrapolating the values for the whole field requires ears to be counted manually, which is prone to subjective evaluation, takes a lot of time and requires large human resources. In the case of larger fields, samples must be taken from more than one location, which additionally slows down the process. The aim of the research was to develop a system for wheat ear recognition and counting, which is necessary step for further estimation of wheat ear coverage density in the field, and yield prediction. Images of winter wheat were taken at 4 dates during the growing season and segmented manually to acquire the ground truth. Image segmentation was done using deep learning. Namely, convolutional neural networks were applied to RGB and thermal images and the results were compared to the ground truth to assess the system accuracy. Development of a comprehensive system for ear counting and yield prediction has a huge practical value for crop monitoring and optimal decision-making in wheat production.

Keywords: phenotyping · deep learning · wheat · yield prediction · segmentation

1 Introduction

Human population is growing, so the topics of monitoring and increasing yield of crops are becoming more and more interesting in the recent years. For the third year in a row, there has been a rise in world hunger [1]. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations adopted the 17 global objectives and goals over the next 15 years (2016-2030) [2]. Priorities are to end hunger, achieve food security and improve nutrition [3]. The investment in agriculture - crops, livestock, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture - is key to accomplishing the entire set of goals [2]. In order to prevent losses, possible solutions are the implementation of tools for risk monitoring and early warning systems in the environment-food-health system [1].

Wheat is one of the most important sources of food worldwide and monitoring of its yield is a significant part of the global plan for nutrition of population [4]. The automatic counting of wheat ears and its yield prediction accordingly can improve crop monitoring. Parameters that are most important for wheat yield estimation are the number of ears, usually per square meter, the number of grains and the 1000 grain weight [5]. The one with the highest correlation with yield is the number of wheat ears per unit area [6].

The conventional method for manual counting is a tedious and labour-intensive task and it is prone to subjective evaluation. Typically, it involves the frame size of 1 m² that is placed over wheat and the ears are counted manually. Estimated number is then extrapolated to the whole field. In the case where the size of a field is larger than a few hectares, the number of ears must be counted at more than one location on the field which additionally slows down the whole process. This method requires not just time, but material and human resources, and limits the usage of such procedure [6]. The automatic counting ears would contribute not just to the velocity of obtaining counts, but would simplify whole process. The counts would also be valuable for the harvest organisation for monitoring plant performance and crop management or in breeding as a phenotyping trait [6].

Deep learning has shown as promising method that outperforms other image analysis and machine learning approaches [7]. The usage of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is increasing and takes a lead in image-based phenotyping: for automatic plant species identification [8], for extracting *Arabidopsis thaliana* phenotyping features [9], [10], or for detecting wheat spikes in controlled environments [11], [12], [13].

In fully connected networks each node in hidden layers is dependent of all pixels, what makes this architecture inappropriate for the image analysis. Convolutional filters solved the problem by restricting dependency only on the pixel's surroundings. This kind of filters usually have small dimensions: 3x3, 5x5 or 7x7, reducing significantly the number of parameters in convolutional neural networks. The filter consists of set of weights that are connected with a part of the inputs. This filter slides through the whole input resulting in new matrix - the feature map [14]. The usage of convolutional filters in hidden layers takes into consideration the context of pixel and thus imitates the work of sensor cells of human eye.

Besides convolutional layers, the choice of the activation function has the big influence on the overall network performance. The Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) is the most utilised activation function for deep neural networks [15]. Results in [16], [17], [18] indicated advantages of this function in training process. ReLU activation function with its variations (*Leaky ReLU*, *Parametrized ReLU*), has shown as computational efficient and very useful for the problem of the vanishing gradient appearing during training procedure. The previous developed activation functions such as linear, step, sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent and softsign activation functions are mostly applied in shallow neural networks.

The aim of our study was to propose and develop a method for automatic counting of wheat ears in outdoor conditions with simplest way of usage, without mounted cameras on vehicles etc. Wheat images should be taken by hand-held cameras or by smartphones' integrated cameras. Here we opt for the first option and as usage of mobile phones is wide-spreading and their functions and gadgets are developing, we expect emerging solutions with smartphones. The system developed in this paper allows farmers to take a photo of their crops and instantaneously get the counts of wheat ears per observed area that are necessary for further yield estimation. More images taken by users would provide the opportunity to capture different densities across field and to develop model with higher prediction accuracy at the field level.

Motivation for the study comes from the fact that the number of ears per unit ground area is one of the main agronomic yield components in determining grain yield. Its fast estimation contributes to monitoring the efficiency of crop management practices, early yield prediction or serves as a phenotyping trait in breeding programs.

2 Related work

Manual counting is a tedious and labour intensive task. The first idea to simplify manual counting on the field dates from 2010[19]. The experiment was setup by positioning the camera at the height of 0.85 m allowed for the area of 0.25 m² to be observed. For image processing and automatic counting the colour and texture image analysis were applied: classical methods of image segmentation and classification combined with morphological ones. In [6] authors applied Laplacian and median filter for preprocessing images, and find local maxima for detection and classification of spikes. In [20] Gabor filters were utilised along with principal component analysis and k-means clustering. In [5] image fusion was used with Twin Support Vector Machines (TWSVM). So far, deep learning found its usage in phenotyping too, so in [7] and [21] convolutional neural network reaches great results in solving this type of problem. In [7] authors used Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN) and RGB images, reaching average accuracy of 93.30 % and F1 score 0.95. The contribution of [21] is not just in developed novel network architecture for this particular usage, but also in creation of the dataset with simple black background in a controlled in-door environment.

There are many factors that have an influence on the recognition accuracy. They include illumination intensity, shadows, noise, different angles for capturing images and observed field-of-view. It is in detail explained in [5] that it is not easy to determine the right angle or the time of image acquisition. In [6] and [7] it has been shown that the nadir perspective is a good solution for the angle of image acquisition. However, our study and few others ([5, 7, 20, 21, 22]) relied on oblique perspective which allows to get more information about colour, shape and texture. This information can be valuable not just for counting ears, but for detection and monitoring of a disease spreading [7].

Focus of related studies was just on the usage of RGB images, only in [6] was mention the potential usage of thermal camera, but it is criticised because of a low resolution and a high cost of those cameras. In our study we decided to use both, RGB and thermal camera, for ear detection and counting. Due to compact shape, ears have a greater thermal capacity than the rest of the plant. Hence, they accumulate heat more slowly than leaves and the stem, but they accumulate more of it and hold it for longer. For this reason, they appear very bright in thermal images and can be easily distinguished from the background, even by human eye [23]. In RGB images on the other hand, ears and the background have similar green colour and their segmentation must rely on more complex parameters, such as the shape and texture. That motivated us to consider both sources of information.

3 Data Collection

3.1 Study areas

Two fields were observed at two locations, in Bajmok (45.97N 19.42E) and in Ravno Selo (45.45N 19.62E), two villages in Vojvodina, the northern province of Serbia. The images were taken at four dates (7th and 17th of May in Bajmok, and 11th and 18th of May in Ravno Selo), two times at each location, in two wheat growth stages: the beginning of flowering, when approximately 10% of flowers were opened and in the early milk stage of wheat. In Bajmok, the average daily maximum temperature in May was 23°C and the average precipitation was 49 mm [24]. In Ravno Selo, the daily maximum average temperature in May was 24°C and the average precipitation 52 mm [25]. The experimental fields were set up in the same way: two seed varieties were planted (*NS40S* developed by Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, Serbia and *Ingenio CCB* Syngenta).

Experimental fields were divided into 16×10 grid, where the first mentioned variety was planted in the first 5 columns, while the second variety was in the remaining 5. That resulted in 80 plots per variety on each field/location. Each plot was the size of 4 m², with 0.2 m space between each column and row. The experiments were conducted in the morning, during cloudless days from 9 AM to noon, to avoid unwanted noise in measurements resulting from illumination differences.

3.2 Experiment setup

The camera used on the field is manual FLIR SC620 camera, with thermal image resolution of 640x480 pixels and RGB image resolution of 2048x1536 pixels. This camera has reading accuracy +-2% of in the temperature range of -40°C to +500°C with the field of view of 24°x18°/0.3m, the focal length of 40mm and with the spatial resolution of 0.65mrad [26]. This type of camera detects very small temperature differences and collects infrared radiation, that is useful to

distinguish and to highlight ears from background. The tripod was set up on maximum height (1.25m) resulting in camera sensor positioned at 0.55m above the wheat canopy (with height \approx 0.7-0.8m at the time of imaging). The images captured approximately under viewing angle of 30° in relation to the horizontal.

During the image acquisition we used automatic setup for illumination, which allowed us to observe the relative temperature difference between ears and the stem. Considering the fact that the process of image acquisition was manual the problem of motion blur appeared during process due to a shaking hand or an unintentional movement of the camera. After discarding the images that had problems with blur or illumination and shadows, 138 images with good quality in both modalities were selected for our experimental evaluation. Examples of thermal and visible images are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Examples of RGB (a) and thermal image (b)

4 Proposed method

In this paper we develop system for wheat-ears detection from thermal and RGB images captured on the field in outdoor conditions. The system consists of two main parts: module for segmentation of image regions belonging to the wheat ears, and module for their counting. Besides these main modules, overall workflow requires image preprocessing, cross-validation and postprocessing steps (see Fig. 2). In the following we give a short description of each of these steps.

4.1 Image Preprocessing

In the image preprocessing step all images were normalised into 0-1 interval. Thermal images were acquired as pseudo coloured images where red and yellow colours represented warmer parts (usually ears), while blue represented background (usually leaves and the stem). This allows better distinction and interpretation of objects in images, which paved a way for easier wheat ear detection.

Fig. 2. Pipeline of the proposed approach step by step

We use only the red channel for the analysis, as the other ones were linearly dependent to it. Color RGB images were originally large, 2048x1536 pixels. Labelling such large images with plenty of ears proved to be too tedious. Therefore, since thermal images cover the central region of RGB images, RGB images were cropped to the same size as thermal images (640x480 pixels) in such way to represent the same field of view as thermal images.

4.2 Segmentation

The image segmentation is one of the most important step in the plethora of pattern recognition algorithms, considering the fact that results of the segmentation affect on the further image analysis and the possible propagation of error [27]. In this paper we did the pixel-based segmentation using the convolutional neural network (CNN). We restrict our segmentation problem only on two labels, one which will denote that observed pixel belongs to the wheat ear and other which indicates that pixel is the part of the background.

In order to test segmentation accuracy a ground truth labels were made manually. The output of the labelling are binary images, where the pixel value of 1 indicates that it belongs to the region of wheat ear, while value 0 denotes the background. Both kinds of images were divided into training and test datasets, 80 % for training and 20 % for test. The average number of ears in thermal images was 80, obtained from total number of 11040 manually counted ears in all selected thermal images (8832 for training and 2208 for testing). The average number of ears in RGB images is 36, obtained from total number of 4968 ears in all selected RGB images (3975 for training and 993 for testing). Difference in resolution of thermal and RGB sensors resulted in lower number of ears in RGB images compared to the thermal images. In the following we give a detail explanation of CNN architecture that we propose.

4.3 CNN architecture

For the problem of ear detection, i.e. segmentation of image region that belong to the ear, we developed our own CNN architecture without using any previous pretrained model from literature. The advantage of used convolutional layers in proposed architecture is that they have far less parameters for learning due to rare connections and shared weights which reduces the computational complexity, saves usage memory and allows faster network learning. Convolutional layer depends on the size of convolutional filter, the number of channels of input image and the number of feature maps [12]. The proposed network consists of blocks of convolutional layers, after each is inserted the activation function. The commonly used activation function for deep neural networks is *Rectified Linear Units* (ReLU) [15] defined as:

$$ReLU(x) = \max(0, x). \quad (1)$$

Besides that ReLU outperforms other activation functions in computational efficiency and in solving problem of the vanishing gradient, it causes production of ‘dead’ neurons. These kind of neurons give the return value equal to 0 for an each sample in database for training. This is happening when we have the negative argument as the input of ReLU activation function, which results in output always equal to 0. The advantage of this ReLU behaviour is that those zeros can be eliminated from the network and in that way a better computational efficiency can be achieved. Then the computations are significantly simplified and reduced to operations such as the comparison, the addition and the multiplication. The disadvantage of this ReLU characteristics is that ‘dead’ neuron can affect the total accuracy of network [18].

A various improvements of ReLU function have been proposed in order to solve the negative aspects of ‘dead’ neurons. Here we will mention the *Leaky ReLU* (lReLU) and *Parametrized ReLU* (PReLU). The lReLU, defined as:

$$lReLU(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha x, & x < 0 \\ x, & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

return the constant value α for a input values bellow zero providing that gradient doesn’t vanish. The hyperparameter α can take the value in the range $[0,1]$ while according to the presented work in [14], the value of α should be set on 0.01. In [28] however is proved that using some other types of data, the bigger values of this parameter works better. The PReLU is another modification of ReLU function which learns the hyperparameter α from the data instead of setting it on the constant value like LReLU did [18].

In this work we opt for a *Exponential Linear Units* (ELU) activation function [15]. The ELU belong to the group of non-linear functions and represent element-wise function [29]:

$$ELU(x) = \max(0, x) + \min(0, \alpha * (\exp(x) - 1)). \quad (3)$$

This activation function speeds up learning in deep neural networks and allows to achieve higher classification accuracy. Usage of ELU has shown to be more robust on noise in the data and achieves better generalization of CNN with more than 5 layers compared to other activation functions [28]. Among blocks of convolutional layers followed by ELU function, a batch normalisation as regularization method is inserted. That provides speed-up in training time and prevent overfitting. In the first convolutional layer a kernel of size 7x7 is used while in others we use kernel size 3x3. The architecture is depicted in Fig 3.

Fig. 3. The proposed CNN architecture.

For a loss function a Binary Cross Entropy is used (see (4)). The losses are averaged and summed over observations for each batch and the function returns a loss per input/target element [30]. This loss function is used because the main problem considered here is to segment or to classify which pixels belong to the ears and which to the background, which is indeed the problem of the binary classification.

$$H_p(q) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i \cdot \log(p(y_i)) + (1 - y_i) \cdot \log(1 - p(y_i))) \quad (4)$$

In equation (4) a y_i represent label (1 for pixels that belong to ears and 0 for background) and $p(y_i)$ is the predicted probability that pixel belongs to the class of ears. For each white pixel (ear region) ($y_i = 1$), the function adds log probability of it being part of ear, $\log(p(y_i))$, to the loss, or $\log(1-p(y_i))$, that is the probability that the pixel belongs to the background ($y_i=0$) [31].

4.4 Measures

Similar as in [5], [7] and [21], usual measures for the evaluation of results are used in this paper. True positive (TP) represents correctly classified a pixel as an ear. False positive (FP) represents incorrectly classified a background pixel as an ear, but multiple detection of the same pixel, as well. False negative (FN)

represents incorrectly classified an ear pixel as a background pixel.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5)$$

Recall is a measure of detected pixels that belong to ears in the image.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

Accuracy measures model performance.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

F1 score (The Srensen-Dice index, Dice similarity coefficient) is a measure that is used for comparing similarities of two samples, in range [0,1]. Considering the fact, that the main problem of this paper is binary classification and segmentation ears of wheat, this measure represents a good estimation of model performance and robustness.

$$F1_{score} = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (8)$$

For showing the relation between counting and a target it is usually used Mean Square Error, but for this problem has not shown as enough representative. So, it is used a relative counting error, as in [20]. For image i , the relative error is defined as [20]:

$$Err(i) = \frac{|y_p(i) - y_t(i)|}{y_t(i)} \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, y_p represents the automatic counted number of ears per image i , y_t is the manual counted number of ears on the observed image i , the true value of wheat ear number.

The accuracy is calculated by [20]:

$$Acc(i) = \begin{cases} \frac{y_p(i)}{y_t(i)}, & \text{if } y_p(i) \leq y_t(i) \\ 2 - \frac{y_p(i)}{y_t(i)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

This definition covers both cases and insures that the value of accuracy stays between 0 and 100 %. In the case that the relative error has the value bigger than 1, that means that the predicted value is too far from the target one [20].

Also, for the evaluation of linear relation between the true and predicted value it is usual to apply Pearson correlation coefficient and the coefficient of determination, which is equal to the squared value of Pearson coefficient. Those measures are used in [7]. Pearson coefficient gives information about of regularity of the relation between data values. The squared value of the Pearson coefficient is the coefficient of determination. The minimum value of this coefficient is 0.25, for the result to be acceptable in practice [32].

5 Results, discussion and future work

5.1 Activation Functions

In this paper we evaluated performance of activation functions from the aspects of memory usage of single GPU and the required time for 10 epoch of training on thermal images. The GPU that is used is one from the set of four NVIDIA TITAN X GPUs.

Fig. 4. a) GPU memory usage performance, b) performances of the model dependent on usage different activation functions. The results are obtained after 10 epochs.

Based on the comparisons on obtained results, we selected ELU activation function, due to better performances than other two activation functions. ELU requires much less memory of single GPU, only 61.17 % of total memory during training process (7457/12189 MiB), which allows usage of deeper network if it is necessary and much faster training while ReLU and PReLU requires 98.70 % of GPUs memory (12031/12189 MiB).

Fig. 5. Measured required time for training process dependent on different activation functions. The results are obtained after 10 epochs.

ReLU requires as similar time on 10 epochs as ELU, but on 1000 epoch, training becomes slower. PReLU requires the longer time for training, considering the fact that the hyperparameter α is also learned during training. ELU activation function is chosen not just because of faster training and less memory usage, but also the fact that these improvements does not affect on performances of model accuracy.

5.2 Segmentation

The deep convolutional network for thermal images achieved results of 75.63 % F1 Score. This measure is the most significant for the first part of the system, for segmentation. Also, the accuracy of the model is 92.59 %, the precision is 85.36%, and recall reached 94.73 %. In the following table these results are shown.

Table 1. Results of segmentation - thermal images

F1score	Accuracy	Recall	Precision
0.75	0.92	0.94	0.85

Fig. 6. a) the original thermal image b) the manual made binary mask c) the output from the model d) the applied threshold of 0.8 on the output

In order to achieve the most precisely segmentation as possible, the threshold is chosen based on the highest reached value of F1 score. The chosen threshold has the value of 0.8 and it is applied on the model output, that is used in the next step, for the automatic counting ears.

For RGB images, the results are slightly different. The model achieved F1 Score 68.46 %, the accuracy 67.74 %, the precision of 70.83%, and recall reached 84.23%. On the output from RGB model the same threshold of 0.8 is applied.

Table 2. Results of segmentation - RGB images

F1score	Accuracy	Recall	Precision
0.68	0.67	0.84	0.70

Fig. 7. a) the original RGB image b) the manual made binary mask c) the output from the model d) the applied threshold of 0.8 on the output

5.3 Counting ears

For ground truth, ears are counted on the original masks, by two people. The mean value is taken as the true value of the number of ears on images. Ears are also counted manually by the same two people, on masks obtained from the model for both types of images. The propagation of error of non-detected ears from the segmentation caused the relative error of 9.5 % for thermal images and 14.33 % for RGB images. The automatic method of counting is done on the output from the model, after the applied threshold of 0.8 and the basic morphological operation - erosion in one iteration with the kernel size of 5x5 for thermal images and 7x7 for RGB images. For thermal images, the automatic method of counting ears has the error of 11.74 % in regard to manual counted ears on masks obtained from the model. Also the automatic counted number of ears reached accuracy of 89.22 % compared to the manually counted ears, The result is summary on all 27 test images. For RGB images, the error is 18.46 % in regard to manual counted ears on masks obtained from the model. Also the automatic counted number of ears accuracy is 82.27 % compare to the manually counted ears on all test images. The results are given in the following table.

5.4 Understanding the algorithms errors

For future improvements of the results it is important to understand reasons for non-detected ears. There are a few challenges in the step of detection of ears. The occlusion and the overlap are the crucial problems that causes errors in segmentation. Different sizes of ears within image due to the perspective of the imaging and different resolutions of thermal and RGB images are additional

Table 3. Results of counting ears - thermal images

Images	Thermal	RGB
True number	80.26	36.58
Image counted number	75.96	36.63
Automatic counted number	72.66	33.95
Accuracy	89.22	82.27
Error	11.74	18.46
Pearson coefficient	0.73	0.64
Coefficient of determination	0.53	0.40

challenges. The angle of image acquisition, the illumination on the field, the time of imaging and others fields conditions also have impact on final results.

6 Conclusion

This research showed that it is possible to use different types of images, thermal and RGB for detection of wheat ears. Proposed approach does not require mounted cameras on vehicles or expensive and complicated set ups. The system for the image acquisition required a hand-held camera and a tripod. It is easy moveable through the plots on the field. The whole approach is significant for plant phenotyping, considering the fact that the number of ears is meaningful for estimating the wheat yield. Our goal is to allow farmers to obtain the number of ears in fast and simple manner that would be an input for as much as possible accurate estimation of wheat yield. This is important not just to plan future harvest, but also to monitor plants for particular stage of growth and prevent lower yields or a disease spreading.

Our future work will be directed towards expanding database with the higher quality images, not just thermal and RGB from FLIR camera, but also those captured by mobile phone. Additional work on the alignment of these images is necessary. That would allow us to make connection with yield related data from the field, such as the amount of grains or their weight. Finally, there is certainly space for the improvement of the segmentation model and the method for automatic counting ears.

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